

Deliverable D2.9

Evaluation of data governance experiences - Report

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1. Executive Summary

The 1+MG Declaration foresees a harmonised data governance for the genomic data infrastructure, which is applicable to all data included into and used from the 1+MG data infrastructure. Data governance is a central element for the entire design of the 1+MG data infrastructure. It influences the legal implementation as well as the IT infrastructure and the information management, which must reflect and enable the workflows of the data governance.

In WP2 of the GDI project, we are developing recommendations for such data governance with respect to the data access procedure for scientific research, healthcare reuse, policy development and quality management as well as governance for inclusion of data into 1+MG and for data use. We aim for an agreement between the national representatives on the governance panel on data governance which is pivotal to prepare the implementation.

This deliverable reports on experience collected from existing national and international data infrastructures with the focus on data access governance. This is based on input gathered in the project HealthData @ EU and complemented by information gathered in a workshop that we organised ourselves. WP2 organised in September 2023 a workshop with representatives from various European data infrastructures for secondary use and 1+MG ELSI Working Group members.

Before the workshop, participants were queried on practical aspects of data governance for secondary use, also beyond research purposes. The results of this survey allow us to conclude that all currently envisaged purposes for secondary use are relevant to generate value from genomic and health data. Among these purposes, scientific research and policy development purposes can build on a similar data governance on the one hand, and so can healthcare reuse and quality management purposes on the other hand. Budget needs to be foreseen will be needed to set up a Data Access Committee (DAC) with dedicated staff at the genomic data infrastructure, to develop IT tools supporting the data governance workflows as well as to generate and provide clear and harmonised information, materials and procedures to applicants. These upfront investments will allow us to reduce administrative costs later caused by incomplete applications and high needs for direct

communications with applicants. Finally, we envisage in principle an open ended retention time for the data, subject to a regular assessment of future usability of the data, to allow the creation of more value from data. The value for future use has to be balanced with capacities, cost and future technical developments.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1 Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2 Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3 Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 4 Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers</p>	Yes

(e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.	
Outcome 5 Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.	No
Outcome 6 Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.	No
Outcome 7 Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.	No
Outcome 8 Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.	No

3. Methods

Data governance is a central element for the design of the 1+MG data infrastructure. It influences the legal implementation and informs choices and design features for the IT infrastructure and the information management, which must reflect and enable the workflows of the data governance. An agreement on the data governance is therefore pivotal to prepare the implementation. Secondary use in the research context is fairly common, but at the same time, it is also the most complex and demanding in its procedures, which has an influence on the infrastructure setup to be built.

There are a number of principles to build on that were clear from the start (each will be indicated by underlined terms in the following paragraphs). Data governance should be designed to reflect international ethical standards and data protection requirements to provide a responsible framework for data reuse. Such an approach is being called "data protection by design and default" (DPbDD) and is a requirement under the GDPR. Other elements relevant to follow is that the procedures should be as flexible as possible to allow for different setups and needs in the countries [flexibility] and at the same time procedures must be as harmonised as necessary to ensure that the infrastructure appears homogeneous towards the outside, i.e. the user's perspective. Data governance must be feasible, which means that, when having to be compliant with the law, it should be implemented in a way that actually works, is competitive and is financially affordable [legal / logistic / financial feasibility], which means the governance must allow to scale [scalability]. In consequence, manual efforts should be minimised. A special role is assigned to the IT infrastructure, to be built by Pillar II, which should enable efficient and automatised or semi-automated workflows and information management. The governance for the IT infrastructure must also allow a workable environment for users and not make data use unnecessarily complicated [technical feasibility].

The IT infrastructure must allow for all the functionalities covering the data life cycle where data governance, data security, feasibility and scalability are relevant design aspects. The entire integrated e-Infrastructure services and data governance is going to be built according to DPbDD principles. It should leverage existing European digital capacities and capabilities wherever possible but new investments will be unavoidable to meet the new challenges of a harmonised governance and the requirements of a federated data infrastructure as envisaged in the 1+MG Declaration. While this may lead to a higher initial investment, it will lower the cost of operations significantly, in particular where tools are designed to become reusable in the context of the European Health Data Space (EHDS). As countries get ready for the establishment of tools and services in the EHDS now (funding provided in the EU4Health programme), national strategies should be made now to which extent tools and services should be independent, interoperable or reusable. Tools may be reused for both EHDS and 1+MG but also the data governance should be compatible because data access governance also shapes the design of the tools. It is therefore important to agree on the data

governance early to translate the data governance requirements into the infrastructure design and implementation.

Based on the workflows and requirements defined in the data governance, interaction with Pillar II will lead to insights on a possible implementation through local, national and central tools in the IT infrastructure of 1+MG.

Our work in GDI WP2 builds on the prior work of the B1MG project and the 1+MG ELSI Working Group, in which we compiled recommendations for dealing with vulnerable subjects and groups¹, a policy for incidental findings² and a policy for the communication of research results.³ The Report on data access and governance framework contains a recommendation for an overarching data governance for research in the 1+MG as derived from the DPbDD approach as well as the policies defined.⁴

This work builds largely on ethical best practice and legal requirements. In this deliverable, we also look into procedural best practice, prior experience and recommendations that can help to provide us with an efficient and scalable data governance that encourages and supports secondary use of data. We also wanted to use the opportunity to learn more about secondary use for a broader scope than research only. The result is a list of elements that will be considered for the data governance to be proposed in WP2.

To complement the work done in B1MG, in this deliverable, we wished to take into consideration current good practices and experiences at existing European data infrastructures for secondary use from a practical point of view in order to select the best practices for the 1+MG data infrastructure. We therefore reviewed the work already performed in projects such as HealthyCloud⁵, the Joint Action TEHDAS⁶, the HealthData@EU Pilot⁷ and work of the Research Data Alliance (RDA)⁸ and the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)⁹. Most of these have pursued surveys on existing practice with a focus on the following aspects: what data are included, what metadata is provided, how to apply, how access decisions are taken, what technical and organisational safeguards are in place, what contractual arrangements etc. We do not want to duplicate all this work. Instead, our aim was to capture in addition the soft factors – what works in practice and what does not, what are the actual hurdles, what works best.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/86447>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/86445>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/86446>

⁴ Link soon to be found on the following webpage: <https://b1mg-project.eu/resources/>

⁵ <https://healthycloud.eu/>

⁶ <https://tehdas.eu/>

⁷ <http://ehds2pilot.eu>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁹ <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

On these questions, the HealthData@EU pilot project that started in October 2022, provided the best input and is also closest to 1+MG in its setup. It brings together 17 partners including designated health data access bodies and health data sharing infrastructures. It aims to pilot the EHDS infrastructure for the secondary use of health data, which will serve research innovation, policy making and regulatory purposes. The HealthData@EU pilot project conducted an extensive survey on existing data infrastructures for secondary use identifying common elements and major differences. This survey covered questions on data types and sources, data discovery / data catalogue, access procedures and application form, contractualisation, data provision and data use as well as transparency / data subject rights. The report is expected to be published shortly; relevant conclusions for GDI are reproduced below.¹⁰

In GDI WP2, we make use of the HealthData@EU survey results and related discussions and complement it with experiences on the practical level. To collect the additional information, PNED compiled a questionnaire on some practical aspects of data governance for secondary use, beyond research purposes, covering:

- Experience with purposes other than scientific research, such as policy development and quality management including differences in the procedures between different categories of purposes
- Timeframe, efforts and actors for/in data access reviews and quality of the review process
- Reasons for and frequency of rejection of data access requests
- Usage of access fees
- Advantages and disadvantages of using secure processing environments rather than data download
- Experience with user misconduct
- Exercising of data subjects' rights
- Choice of data retention
- Ethics approvals and other topics that participants may want to raise.

The questions were distributed to the participants of the 1+MG ELSI WG meeting on 12th September 2023 in Brussels, in advance of the meeting. Some countries provided input on the questionnaire in writing. At the meeting, the WP2 Leads organised a dedicated session to query representatives of countries/organisations on their experience and recommendations for data governance in order to learn how data access is given in the countries already. This group was chosen because the members are nominated by the 1+MG Signatory Countries to provide input into the design of policies

¹⁰ The summary of the legal landscape analysis can be downloaded here: [HealthData@EU Pilot identifies common elements for health data access and data use within the legal frameworks of the participating nodes - EHDS2 Pilot - Official website](#)

and data governance of 1+MG. They have a reach-through to national mirror groups, thus tapping into an even wider pool of experts on the national level.

This deliverable builds on both the written answers and the discussion in the meeting as well as the HealthData@EU survey. The input received was evaluated for its relevance to fit the above criteria for the data governance of the 1+MG data infrastructure. Another aim was to receive more input towards data purposes beyond research as the work on data governance in the B1MG project was mainly focussed on research use. In addition, any input relevant for legal and ethical compliance that leads to elements to be considered for the 1+MG data governance is important. The analysis led to a digest of main elements that could be seen as “take home messages” for further consideration. These digests were once again verified with the 1+MG ELSI Working Group both in writing and in a meeting.

The output of this deliverable will be input for the discussion with the GDI Pillar I Working Group of governmental representatives as well as Pillar II for the options of implementation. The considerations on the information and interaction with users will be relevant in particular for WP4, which designs and builds the user portal in the GDI project. The data governance related procedures and “ELSI” metadata will feed into the data management in WP6. Also the tools and workflows on the national level as targeted in WP3 will be influenced as well as the overall set-up as addressed in WP5.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Input from HealthData@EU experiences

Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, BBMRI-ERIC (WP7 Lead of HealthData@EU) provided preliminary results from the EHDS HealthData@EU Pilot project that followed a similar approach of first investigating current (good) practices with regard to the user journey. The survey received input from the following resources: BBMRI-ERIC (Biobanks and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure Consortium)¹¹, DE (Health Data Lab /Forschungsdatenzentrum Gesundheit)¹², DK (Danish Health Data Authority)¹³, FI (FinData)¹⁴, FR (Health Data Hub)¹⁵, BE (Sciensano)¹⁶, NO (Health Data Service; Norwegian Directorate of eHealth)¹⁷ and HR (Croatian Institute of Public Health)¹⁸. From this survey a landscape analysis identifies common elements and major differences between the national health data access bodies, Input for this deliverable was also derived from the survey results as provided by BBMRI and discussions in the HealthData@EU directly.

¹¹ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>

¹² <https://www.healthdatalab.de/>

¹³ <https://sundhedsdatastyrelsen.dk/da/english>

¹⁴ <https://findata.fi/en/>

¹⁵ <https://www.health-data-hub.fr/>

¹⁶ sciensano.be

¹⁷ <https://helsedata.no/en/>

¹⁸ <https://www.hzjz.hr/en/>

The following findings were made.

- Data infrastructure can become a national silo [e.g. if requests must be filed in local language or processing is required to take place on national infrastructure].
Some resources limit the access requests to the national language. Here, not only the instructions and the data access request form are relevant but basically all software components with user relevance, contracts and many more aspects are all part of the user relevant framework that is being created. This significantly influences the use of the resources beyond the country. In DK, the primary data providers often require that a Danish national researcher must be involved as collaborator if data are to be made available beyond Denmark. In Finland, the requirement to use the national certification body for a secure infrastructure means that a download of data into an alternative secure processing environment requires that the target system fulfils the Finnish security specifications, which includes a certification by the Finnish data security assessment body. This limits the pooling of data from different resources where these are all "locked" in their own secure processing environments..
- Different templates and organisation of access request handling can make a big difference for handling speed
With the exception of FR, the data protection authorities (DPAs) are usually not involved in the data access decision. The process may, however, involve institutional data protection officers (in case of AT), institutional ethics committees and national or regional ethics committees. This leads to small differences in procedures and templates, e.g. consent forms, between institutions of the same country, which may, however, have a large impact on decision-making. The experience is also that the involvement of official bodies like data protection authorities will more likely lead to delays than dedicated data access committees.
- So far, no harmonisation of Ethics approval procedures is achieved
An EU-wide harmonised ethical approval form and procedures are currently not foreseen. There are cultural differences across Europe, a general lack of willingness to harmonise is observed and there is also a lack of funding to support harmonisation. Even within a country and within an organisation's ethics committee, procedures and opinions might differ so that decisions vary and the justification is often difficult to follow. So far, harmonisation is only implemented for clinical trials.
- Decision making timeframes depend largely on the scope of interaction with users
Reviews take anywhere between a few weeks and 6 months. It was clarified that the time frames typically do not take into account the time needed to obtain ethics approval and to establish a common understanding of what the researcher wants. If that is considered too, about 3-6 months can be added. Delays are caused by a number of things from unclear research questions to the necessity to explain PhD students how to actually apply.

- Quality of access requests is crucial but often lacking
Many reports were given on the insufficient quality of data access requests. It is generally agreed that more education and training of researchers, in particular young researchers, on ethical issues is needed, which requires additional resources that are lacking. The quality of access requests leads to considerable delay. There is also a misalignment between the required resources for such an effort and the available funding. However, such general education falls outside the remit of a specific data infrastructure for secondary use and should be addressed in curricula of scientists.
- Assessment of the qualification of applicant is usually left to the host institution
Mostly, the qualification of the applicant is not considered a review criterion. Where the host institution deems the employee sufficiently qualified, this is not questioned in the access review. Only in DK, the level of experience, support and resources of the applicant factors into the decision. However, only where an applicant has no host institution (e.g., in case of healthcare professionals), their qualification is really decisive. Otherwise, the responsibility can be left to the employer.
- Secure processing environments become more common
The provision of a secure processing environment is increasingly common for repositories which have a legal mandate to make data available. This goes along with the wish to keep better control of what happens to the data. Some countries are already investing in developing existing e-Infrastructures to support sensitive data processing services for research data that needs protection, as for example 1+MG does. However, secure processing environments can also lead to silos where data become "locked" in different repositories and the computational needs and/or necessity for federated computing cannot be fulfilled for a certain project, which can easily happen for large-scale genomic analyses. .
- Models towards access fees vary enormously
While some repositories do not charge any fees in general, others charge only certain users but not others (e.g., public authorities; public sector bodies; students). Some charge all users equally.
The charges may cover only the administrative effort of the access request handling, in other cases, also the data services and processing is charged. The latter is charged typically per hour of effort, which can sum up substantially. Charges of up to 50k EUR were reported.
- Data breach
A data breach can lead to a blockage for future requests by the applicant. Such blocking can be either temporary or permanent. However, if an applicant is excluded from further data access as a natural person, it requires a feedback loop on the level of the individuals, which does not exist in all countries. It is more common to penalise the entire user institution, thereby impacting other individuals as well. Blocking individual users on a European level is

currently still difficult to establish as individual researchers cannot be traced where they change their host institutions. Already now, Incident response protocol and subsequent rehearsal between the distributed infrastructure services is a foreseen exercise.

4.2 Input derived from the 1+MG ELSI Working Group

In this section we describe the additional input received through our own survey and a dedicated discussion session between members of the 1+MG ELSI Working Group. In the discussions we covered input from the experience in the following data resources: BBMRI¹⁹, the Danish National Genome Centre²⁰, the Dutch Pathology Archives²¹, the data registries under the Estonian Ministry of Health, the Finnish Biobank (THL)²², the **French Genomic Medicine Initiative**²³, the data registries under the Maltese Ministry of Health and the data registries of the Swedish Regions. Participants also reported from access review experience in ethics boards. Experts gave insight into their experience with the access procedures already in place in the countries and provided recommendations for the development of a governance for the 1+MG data infrastructure implementation.

The input is given here in nine subsections numbered i through ix, each describing first the subset of topics addressed, followed by a table of written input received and a narrative of the outcomes of the discussions in the workshop.

i. Different purposes for data access

Subjects addressed

- What experience do countries have with purposes other than scientific research?
- Do they have criteria of what qualifies for which purpose? In particular, are there examples of access questions for policy development or quality management that need access to personal data? Could this apply also to genome data?
- To what extent is there a difference in the data access request / review procedures between the different categories of purposes? If so, what is different and does it affect the list of criteria to be checked? How does that influence the review process in terms of information and efforts?

Answers:

MT	Applications may have a variety of purposes, including policy development as well as research and development by commercial entities. The main aim is to create more value
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¹⁹ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>

²⁰ <https://eng.ngc.dk/>

²¹ <https://www.palga.nl/>

²² <https://thl.fi/en/web/thl-biobank>

²³ <https://pfmq2025.aviesan.fr/en/>

	from data. The approval process is identical for all applications. An ethical review is always required, including from ministries and other public bodies, if not covered by Art. 9.2(h) GDPR. Audits for quality assurance are considered to be covered by Art. 9.2(h) and therefore do not require ethics approval.
EE	EE has also a strict ethics approval regime for policy development. Examples for cases of unethical applications for access to genomic data were given such as the investigation of the deduction of criminal tendencies from genomic data, including matching such data to other data records (e.g. criminal records, sexual activities). Thus, policy development as a purpose should be eligible, but regulated in the same way as scientific research applications.
SE	Sweden has registries for quality and statistics on the regional level, which healthcare providers can use for quality management of their work.
DK	In DK, all activities in the primary sector are considered to be primary use and do not require ethics approval. This includes quality measures in healthcare. Research on genomic data, however, is secondary use and requires ethics approval. For registry based data, no ethical approval is needed, based on public interest. There are cases where it is either difficult to distinguish between the purposes of quality assurance, policy development and research or where the actors are involved in both research and policy development. Access for healthcare is easier. However, that bears the danger that clinician scientists may want to use this access to bypass the more laborious research access request. There is no direct industry access. So far no applications have been received for policy development or quality management.
FI	When making data available for secondary use purposes, the source, i.e. if the data was produced in research, medical or another setting, also plays a role. Whether or not the collection was based on consent is also relevant In general, the biobank may give access for other (R&D) purposes and the procedures and the requested details are the same for all purposes. An example for a rejected application is a request for genomic data for an education-related intervention study.
FR	The French Genomic Medicine Initiative started with access for research purposes only. However, most researchers that deposit data are also clinicians. Thus, it is planned to give full access to clinicians in the context of healthcare. Beyond the pure scientific research projects, there have already been access requests for socio-economical projects to generate probabilities and statistics and assess the impact of the French initiative on the benefits of medical treatment.

NO	<p>All activities in the primary sector with primary purposes are considered to be primary use and do not require ethics approval. This includes quality measures in healthcare. Health research requires ethics approval from regional ethical committees, regardless of whether the data is from patient records, health registers for secondary data or use (a relatively large number both with and without consent) or the material is from biobanks. Research on genomic data requires consent, while it is possible to apply for exemption from the duty of confidentiality for other health data. Access can be granted after application to data from patient records, including genomic data, also for other purposes than research. These include statistics, health analyses, development and use of clinical decision tools (AI), quality improvement, planning, management or preparedness to promote health, prevent disease and injury or provide better health and care services. Data from health registers for secondary use can be used for the same purposes, apart from development and use of clinical decision tools (AI). Health Data Service has the authority to grant access and give exemption from the duty of confidentiality to data from health registers for secondary use where such data is linked with data from patient records. There can be some confusion about the regulations, the many actors involved and what is considered as health research and other purposes.</p>
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Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

Benchmarking should be considered as a valid purpose for access requests where it aims at quality management. Even though many institutions based their benchmarking on healthcare quality indicators such as those provided by the OECD rather than analyse raw data directly, it cannot be excluded that comparisons are established based on raw data.

The reason that many data repositories segregate in the procedures between healthcare and quality management of healthcare on the one hand and policy development and research on the other could be based on the permission to process health and genetic data provided by Art. 9.2 GDPR.

- Art. 9.2.h GDPR includes the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems. In consequence, quality management of healthcare can be seen as being subject to Art. 9.2.h GDPR and ethics approvals will not be needed.
- Policy development for healthcare and the healthcare system on the other hand falls typically under Art. 9.2.i GDPR, scientific research under Art. 9.2.j GDPR. Both require suitable safeguards. Ethics approvals belong to important organisational measures to be applied to safeguard the rights and freedoms of data subjects and therefore be considered for both, Art. 9.2.i and 9.2.j GDPR. Ethical issues can arise from the linking of data from different sources, which leads to new information that may be sensitive. Such linking is often an element of both policy development and scientific research.

The separation between the different categories of purposes is not always easy. Policy development, epidemiology and scientific biomedical and health research may be interlinked and overlapping. Scientific research as compared to a broader scope of research that also comprises policy development is suggested to be the aim to generate generalisable knowledge on specific questions and with the intent to publish the results. Such published research results, however, may also be used by governmental bodies for policy development, which demonstrates that multiple purposes can be fulfilled by such projects.

The scope of purposes and data users envisaged for the 1+MG data infrastructure considers all applications and users that can lead to better healthcare.²⁴ This choice is confirmed by meeting participants. Policy development, for example, should not be seen merely as an exercise by public authorities. Policy research also takes place in the private sector, in particular in the USA. A well-known player is the Boston Group²⁵. They look at population level datasets to find the best return for investment, and give recommendations for health policies. The applications can be quite varied. Apart from commercial users, also commercially oriented purposes are seen as important beyond pre-competitive research: device development from data contributes to better and cheaper healthcare (e.g. decision support systems).

When obtaining consent for data inclusion in 1+MG, either as GDPR legal basis or as opt-in / opt-out, no granular options should be offered. Similar to the EHDS, purposes could be described only on the level of the categories such as “scientific research for health”, “policy development for healthcare and healthcare systems”. More granular options are difficult to administer. This applies in particular, where differences are made between types of recipients such as commercial companies, public authorities or public bodies. All possible types of recipients would have to be differentiated for each category of purposes separately. However, some data subjects have concerns where data are processed by commercial companies or public authorities. These concerns could be met by allowing an opt-out to individual data use. Information could be made available through an information portal where data subjects receive information on the individual data use. In such a portal, data subjects could set their information notices with a focus on those types of data use or recipients where they potentially have concerns.

Other considerations are on potential purposes that could be pursued with synthetic data. Currently, there is a limited capacity in the EU to generate synthetic data. However, the usefulness of synthetic data depends on the quality of how many features of the targeted data are reflected and the purpose pursued. Where, for example, research looks into the aetiology of diseases, synthetic data may not have preserved the very feature that is relevant. Thus, synthetic data is useful for building the infrastructures and testing procedures, as is done in GDI, as this is in line with the data minimisation principle of the GDPR.

²⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/86444>

²⁵ <https://www.bcg.com/industries/public-sector/overview>

ii. Data access review procedures

Subjects addressed

- Timeframe and efforts for data access reviews: How long does the review take? What leads to delays? What are the required efforts? What kind of requests require the most effort?
- Actors in data access review: Who is involved, e.g. data providers, ethics committees, DPAs, legal advisors, patient representatives? How is the decision-making organised? How are conflicting opinions handled?
- Quality aspects: What influences the quality or time frames of feedback? How is the DAC composed, both in terms of number of people and formal qualification?

Experiences and suggestions

FR	<p>The Ethical and Scientific Committee is composed of 20 members including patient representatives for rare diseases, lawyers, legal researchers, ethics experts, population genetic experts, bioinformatics experts, information security experts, clinical researchers and other experts representing a diversity of competencies as required. In this Committee, two evaluators are chosen as reporters for each data access request., they perform an in-depth review of the request and raise important concerns towards the Committee.</p> <p>On average, access decisions take ca. 3,5 months. This usually includes 2 evaluations by the Ethical and Scientific Committee. The first review is often limited to clarifying and completing the application where details on methodology and preliminary results are missing. Further efforts go into ensuring that the applicants understand the data sufficiently for pursuing meaningful research.</p> <p>The limitation to secure processing environments also leads to delays. Applicants often do not know how they work in the secure processing environment infrastructure where their team does not include bioinformatics experts.</p>
MT	<p>Reviews are performed by an own ethical body of the Ministry, which is mostly composed of academics from outside the Ministry.</p> <p>With respect to time frames, the problem of external dependencies is raised. Where the Ministry acts as a clearing house, it can move much faster than in cases where data are obtained from hospitals. In the latter case, the Ministry has no control and cannot guarantee any deadlines.</p>
BBMRI	<p>From experience, the most common roadblocks are: the procedure is not available in English, there are no harmonised procedures for application and assessment and applications and decisions are made on a case by case basis. An observation is that those</p>

	<p>biobanks that operate under a clear business model defining access and use conditions are working well and successfully. A lack of resources is certainly an aspect as well. Sometimes one determines the other. However, some biobanks are only run as a byproduct of the work of a researcher or clinician and these should actually not be classified as "infrastructure".</p> <p>In addition, further delays are caused by the low quality of applications received, e.g. unclear purpose, unclear methodology, unclear data needs.</p>
NL	<p>The Dutch Pathology Archive has a two-step set-up where applications must pass a scientific evaluation before a subsequent ethics review is performed. The frequency of meetings plays a role for the speed of feedback. The Dutch Pathology Archives committee meets for example only 6 times a year. The quality of applications varies strongly, with many applications omitting the state-of-the-art literature review, which then leads to significant delays in the time to decision, considering the gap of two months between meetings.</p> <p>An observation is made that a lack of resources affects the speed and diligence of feedback.</p>
GR	<p>Similar observations were made with ethics committees in Greece: the review procedure is often delayed by the lack of human resources and/or of expertise on the side of the reviewers.</p> <p>On the side of the applicants, education on ethics issues as well as dedicated project budgets for ethics work are needed.</p>
EE	<p>The biggest hurdle for the review work and its speed is the quality of the applications.</p>
FI	<p>The review currently involves the data contributors, but it is intended to establish an independent committee in order to avoid conflicts of interest in the future. The quality of the feedback by the data contributors varies very much.</p> <p>The review takes 1-2 months plus time for the formulation of the decision and signature of the MTA (material transfer agreement). Delays could be reduced by providing the reviewers with specific questions for the review.</p>
DK	<p>Reviews of access requests are performed internally at the NGC (National Genome Centre). Delays usually result from insufficient details in the applications, e.g. lack of approvals or pending complex data ownership, missing ethical approvals, delayed institutional approval of projects. Many applications are submitted incomplete as it is well known that additional information will be requested. However, by far the biggest delay is due to the contractual arrangements for processing the data in the DNGC analytics platform. Since data must be accessed in a secure processing environment hosted by DNGC a contract needs to be agreed upon, specifying costs and financial liabilities, between DNGC and the user's host institution.</p>

	NGC approves data access requests based on prior ethical approval of the project and vetting based on "data authorizations". Access is generally granted if the right approvals are available, the purpose of the request is within PM and the vetting checks out.
NO	For health research, there are regular meetings of the research ethics committee and a predictable timeframe. For other purposes, there can be a longer time frame due to considerations/capacity about data from patient records in the Directorate of Health. The newly established Health Data Service is customised to grant data effectively. An additional time factor is that considerations from the data protection officer in each institution can take time.

Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

There are two approaches proposed for dealing with insufficient applications:

- When an application is sent back to the applicant, the clock should be stopped and, where revision is not received in time, the application should expire. Revision requests should be justified containing clear information on the concerns raised by the reviewers and how to address them.
- Incomplete applications are rejected and the applicants invited to send a revised submission, resetting the clock. The timeline should only start with the submission of a valid and complete application.

In order to keep timelines down, also in view of KPIs of the future infrastructure, the second option is more favourable for the infrastructure. Otherwise, each loop may add time on the clock and bring the infrastructure closer to the legally allowed limits. On the other hand, the rejection is discouraging for the applicant. Following a discussion of both approaches, a compromise is suggested that the applicant should be able to easily reopen the previous application and rectify all the insufficient elements and resubmit. For a smooth and satisfactory access procedure, it will be vital that the feedback provided by the infrastructure is clear and helpful.

However, further and considerable delay is usually caused after access review, when data agreements are set up between the platform and the user. Depending on the relationship and capacities on both sides, such contract negotiations between legal departments can be an incalculable source of delay. Finally, preparing the data for release, through merging, harmonising and pseudonymisation, also requires substantial efforts.

iii. Data user and data use – Rejection of an access request

Subjects addressed

- What are the most frequent reasons for a rejection?

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- How many % of applications are rejected?
- Is there a difference between purposes? Does it depend on the type of requester?
- Which preventive measure could reduce the number of rejections?

Experiences and suggestions

FI	Rejections are most frequently caused by research plans that do not correspond to the research area of the biobank, by a request for a large amount of data with inadequate description of the intended use, and by lack of clarity on the nature of a commercial company. Purely policy applications are often rejected with the reason of not being relevant. However, only few applications are rejected (2-5%), but modifications to the application are requested. Applications are increasingly rejected because the research plan is deficient in relation to the quantity or quality of the data requested. Counselling in the form of direct discussions with researchers (not email) helps to reduce the risk of rejection.
DK	Rejections, or rather delays, usually relate to administrative issues, not the substance of the request. In total, there have been none to very few rejections so far, for example due to lack of proper approval. Good communication, clear and accessible guidelines as well as prior discussion help to reduce the risk of rejection.
FR	Only 1 rejection out of 9 submissions so far with the reason that the described project was not scientific, but rather a facilitator of a process. Communication about the infrastructure reduces the risk of rejection.
BBM RI	A big problem is that often applications do not even have a clear research question, which would make it unethical to let them proceed. Covid days with the frantic activities meant that 9 out of 10 applications were rejected. However, that happened typically already on the level of the ethics review. Where the threshold of the ethics review is passed already before the consideration of access approval, the problems are often more on the administrative level as other countries also reported. This typically leads to more negotiations and exchange but not necessarily to rejections.
NO	Rejection happens very rarely. It doesn't depend on the type of requester but on the level of knowledge. The more complicated a project is the more guidance is needed and sometimes this leads to rejection/partial rejection because the applicant doesn't have sufficient knowledge.

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Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

As the majority of applications are suffering from low quality, missing information, and not following the described procedure and templates, it is shortly discussed if AI might be an option for the first line of review, filtering out such invalid requests.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

It is stated that a main reason for the low quality is that applications are delegated to the PhD students rather than pursued by the principal investigators themselves. It is agreed that students should receive a systematic education in ethics and data protection as part of the research training. Currently, not enough consideration and in particular funds are given to this. Ideally, curricula in biomedicine should be adapted accordingly.

There are data infrastructures who build in training elements in their access. Sage Biosciences has a data protection training module as a gateway to achieve access. A test must be passed before access is given. Test questions are changed if an applicant fails in the first round to encourage people to give proper attention to the training.

iv. Data user and data use – Access fees

Subjects addressed

- Are access fees being used?
- What is the typical context where access fees are charged? Healthcare vs research? Purposes other than research?
- Are access fees known in advance? How are they determined? What is the range of access fees?
- Do access fees cover the actual costs?
- Can access fees be prohibitive?

Experiences and suggestions

FI	The biobank has a fixed rate for the access review and charges an hourly rate for extracting and preparing the data.
MT	The Ministry provides data free of charge whereas the Statistics Offices charges. Fees put younger researchers at a disadvantage, which is reflected in the difference in the number of applications obtained. Also, we have experience that applicants try to circumvent fees with creative approaches, e.g. freedom of information rights.
DK	Access fees are mostly well accepted in Denmark. Applicants pay for usage of NGC cloud and researchers are even offering to pay more in order to get data sooner. There is a danger of delays where repositories must use their own in-house administrative resources not aimed for secondary use to provide access. Access fees can help to employ staff for the task and allow scaling-up of the operations. The charging of fees also imposes an obligation of delivering in time.
IE	In Ireland, different fees are charged by the research ethics committee for private enterprises and for public bodies, respectively. However, currently the administrative costs for collecting the lower fees are higher than the fees themselves, thus it is planned to drop the fees for public bodies and increase the fees for private enterprises instead.

NO	Health data service has a flat fee for all applications (1500 NOK excluding VAT for one data source and 3000 NOK for multiple data sources), but to handle the request this can be increased based on the numbers of working hours, 1155 NOK p/h for the data handling. The prices are listed on a web site and they give an estimate of the time needed per project. This doesn't cover the actual cost, only the actual project. The rate for applications to Health Data Service can be prohibitive.
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Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

While on the one hand, the problems for young researchers to have the necessary funds is pointed out as well as the problem to apply for funding where the final charges are not known, also the cost for salaries needs to find considerations. The cost of delivering the data can be minimal compared to the cost of having a research project that is stalled. One needs to consider researchers or PhD students whose salary is on a single project, which cannot move for lack of access.

The possibility for having predetermined rates is considered but discarded if the fees should be related to the actual cost. The complexity of the application and the extraction of data is difficult to be framed in advance.

The recommendation is given that the possibility of different access fees for commercial and non-commercial research, academic research or public interest research is worth exploring. The EU Data Governance Act²⁶ allows such distinctions. However, legal permission is not the only aspect to be considered. Access fees for commercial entities is often perceived as "selling data to industry", thus undermining trust. A careful analysis is necessary before any decision is made.

The user cost analysis in the discussion did not consider (yet) the cost of providing computational service access to the data, just the data access authorisation and data preparation. Countries have varied approaches on how the data can be made actionable (e.g. AI model development). As 1+MG data infrastructure processes sensitive data, external audits for the security setup are a must and a certified secure processing environment is required where data may be pooled from several countries (recommendations of the 1+MG data governance). If the users are expected to cover computing services in addition to the data access request part, it will likely create a blocker at least for starting health research groups in the short term future (e.g. first 5 years of 1+MG service operations).

²⁶ [EUR-Lex - 32022R0868 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R0868)
(<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022R0868>)

v. Data user and data use - Secure Processing Environment (SPE)

Subjects addressed

- Are there any experiences with the use of secure processing environments where data are accessed without download?
- What are the limitations? What are the advantages beyond keeping control?

Experiences and suggestions

MT	Clear advantages are seen that secure processing environments (SPE) require less bandwidth and therefore less cost if the SPE and the data are on the same server. This does not only apply to genomic data but also imaging. It is not feasible to have multiple copies of large datasets.
DK	An advantage for the user also is better scalability of projects using SPEs as well as independence from institutional IT support. The data provision in an SPE is an incentive for data providers who are not comfortable with sharing data with scientific institutions on the scientific institutions' systems. They may be more willing to do that in a secure processing environment. On the other hand, costs related to SPE usage can be more difficult to fund. In addition, the amount of data may make sharing prohibitively expensive.
FI	A disadvantage is that different systems do not always allow federated data analysis, thereby restricting which analyses can be done with data from different organisations. Where data can be downloaded, the system/infrastructure must pass an audit by an organisation accredited in Finland first, which greatly complicates cross-border sharing.
FR	For data from healthcare, even if pseudonymised, France has higher requirements than for data from research. For healthcare data, the IT infrastructure needs to be certified.
NO	The main rule is to provide anonymous data or use SPEs. There are several SPEs (TSD, SSB, Hunt Cloud etc.), but it is not a requirement to use a SPE. Use of SPE is included in the overall assessment of the project.

Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

There is an increasing need for compute capabilities, which leads to a trend to externalise. Small institutions may never afford to process the data if it is not in a secure environment provided externally. Secure processing environments can advance to a place where people want to bring data because it allows them to use a secure environment, which is also comparatively cheap because it scales to many users. For the cost, the certification of a secure processing environment needs to be considered, which can be very expensive, particularly if the computing capabilities need to be advanced like in analysing genomic data and certified data preprocessing pipelines are needed.

vi. Data user and data use – Misconduct by users

Subjects addressed

- Were there cases of misconduct in secondary use of data? What happened and how was it handled?
- Did it change future decisions?

Experiences and suggestions

MT	There was never an actual case of misconduct detected where data were misused after disclosure. The only cases are applications that are already suspicious upfront. These applications are difficult to handle as rejections must be properly and objectively justified.
DK	The NGC has not yet had any cases of users trying to abuse the system. Users trying to circumvent application requirements are the only cases known that could be seen as misconduct on the side of the users. This requires a close watch of purpose limitations.
NO	No information about such projects committing misconduct.

Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

A discussion concludes that in case of misconduct, it should be possible to exclude individual users from further access but not necessarily the user's host institute. It would not be fair if an entire research institution is taken hostage for a single rogue researcher.'

An incident response exercise is recommended to be tested in the federated infrastructure early on.

vii. Best practice

Subject addressed

- Are there things you would like to change in the current system?

Experiences and suggestions

BBM RI	Procedures and guidelines should be as detailed as necessary, but as simple as possible. Clear deadlines, clear feedback loops and clear procedures are needed which put the scientists first. No additional ethics approval should be required. A clear business model and internal quality assessment are recommended.
MT	Feedback loops for users are important.

FI	Better data management systems are needed.
DK	Challenges around orchestrating how different projects can work together on NGC's systems need to be addressed. In general, the service catalogue should provide detailed answers on process, requirements, costs, timelines etc.
FR	More experts are needed for the pre-review. Guidelines should be regularly reviewed and improved based on applicants' feedback regarding their clarity and understandability.
NO	A complicated system with many actors involved needs sufficient resources and knowledge on a permanent basis. This will ensure an equal understanding of the terms, equal practice and prevent ambiguities.

Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

A high investment seems necessary for an efficient system that can scale. To build this, the experience made in the field already will be vital. This is an ambitious goal but in line with the vision of the 1+MG initiative.

The use of artificial intelligence should be considered to answer questions about the data and the procedures. It may be able to capture standard questions where applicants do not read the available materials. Another thought is the use of AI to do the first screening of access applications. Some resources have 45 or more questions in the application. A red / orange / green light screening could be done automatically to flag potential issues before passing the application to the next phase.

The infrastructure should establish an internal quality assessment, to identify where procedures can be simplified, where applicants have difficulties and where else there are possible improvements. Some information, such as reasons for rejection, could be captured in a machine readable way to support such an analysis.

viii. Data subjects' rights

Subject addressed

- Is there any experience with data subjects exercising any rights on the data in data repositories?
- If so, do you know what kind of requests were received?

Experiences and suggestions

MT	Exercising data subjects' rights happens very rarely, maybe 3 requests in 20 years. When requests were sent, then subjects asked which data about the person was stored. The questions never extended towards asking about any data shares.
DK	The National Genome Centre is approached by citizens, with the question if DNGC holds any data of that individual. For most of these requests, it is not the case, since these individuals have not had a WGS analysis conducted. Due to the information package given to patients, when given a WGS analysis in a clinical setting, patients are informed and thus aware if their data are in the DNGC Genome Database.
BBM RI	The withdrawal of data happens very rarely and, if so, is usually linked to a public scandal around a certain institution or research domain. A larger number of requests for deletion were received for the Austrian electronic health records following the anti-vaccination campaigns during the COVID-19 pandemic.
FI	Requests for information on mutations or other health-affecting information related to individual diseases have been made. The requesters are informed that such information can be provided, but without validation nor any guarantee of its accuracy. Some requesters have subsequently withdrawn their request.
SE	Very few opt-outs from the national quality registries so far. This may be due to a great deal of trust from patients in the registries and a desire to contribute to new knowledge about diseases and medical measures, but it can not also be ruled out that many patients are not aware that they appear in quality registries.
NL	Maybe two cases of major opt-outs until now. However, on the national level the same "loss of trust" related opt outs on the level of the healthcare system were observed. The discussion around centralisation of electronic health records or the collection of genetic data led to opt-out waves in the Netherlands.
FR	None so far.
NO	Happens rarely, but they do happen. All kinds of requests are received.

Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

The opt outs have in most cases nothing to do with the data that was collected for the specific project but is because the trust has eroded in an institute or in research as a whole.

ix. Data retention

Subject addressed

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- What determines the data retention period in data repositories?

Experiences and suggestions

FR	The retention time is determined by the data protection authority. For research purposes, it is fixed at 20 years at the time of collection and data cannot be used after that without prior anonymisation. Genomic data has to be deleted because it cannot be anonymised. There is no possibility to extend the deadline. Only aggregated data may be retained longer. For healthcare purposes, data is kept continually.
DK	Data are stored and used for clinical purposes with a retention period of 30 years., but persons may opt-out for research activities.
MT	Retention times are determined by researchers and are between 2-10 years maximum. There is a possibility to request an extension if there are further studies but, depending on the consent obtained, it may mean re-consenting. Patient files are kept up to 10 years after the death of the person. There sometimes are requests to access these data to treat living relatives. They may also be used to compile case reports of the deceased patient.
NO	Data is stored and used for clinical purposes indefinitely, but persons may opt-out for research activities. In health registries for secondary use the data are stored for unlimited periods. It also depends if the registry is consent based.

Further input provided by the group beyond the national set-up

The necessity or custom to have fixed retention times for research is questioned in the meeting. There is a consensus that, rather than having fixed timeframes, it should be possible to keep data available in a repository as long as they are useful in secondary use, subject to the agreement of the data subjects and the availability of funding to operate data services with staff needed. Accountability under the GDPR means that regular checkpoints should be established to see if this criterion is still fulfilled and an external board may be needed to review this but it seems not appropriate to delete data that are still valuable for secondary use and where also the data subjects have no concerns.

It is further discussed that data subjects should be able to ask if their data are kept. Such an offer will likely include contractual arrangements and potentially handling fees on the side of the data holder.

5. Results

From the input provided through the surveys and the discussion in the meeting, the major elements with relevant influence on the 1+MG data governance were identified under consideration of the feasibility criteria, the current existing gaps in the B1MG recommendations on data governance that focus for data access on research only and elements that add to ethical and legal compliance

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implications. The following main considerations were derived and will be taken into account for the design of the future data governance of the 1+MG data infrastructure when discussing with other stakeholders and formulating recommendations for implementation.

Different purposes for data access

- The scope envisaged by 1+MG covering scientific research, policy development, healthcare reuse and quality management is seen as relevant and worth pursuing. The impact of data should be maximised. This principle should apply in general where public benefit can be achieved and no harm for data subjects implied. This recommendation emphasises the currently envisaged scope of the 1+MG initiative.
- Information and opt-in/opt-out options should be done on the level of categories of purposes (i.e. scientific research to improve health, policy development for healthcare and healthcare systems, etc.), similar to the granularity of the EHDS. Concerns of data subjects about commercial actors could be met on the level of information on individual projects.
- Policy development should not be seen as exclusively performed by public bodies / authorities; consulting companies may make relevant contributions.
- Policy development, epidemiology and health research should be considered to be treated equally in the application, which means that they both should require an ethics review. The examples given are convincing and demonstrate that policy development may raise ethical issues and borders between these fields of research and policy development can be blurred.
- Re-use related to healthcare (including quality management of healthcare) can be pursued fairly directly; no ethics review is needed.
- Purpose limitation needs to be watched. In this context, it is particularly important to keep the "easy access" for clinical purposes separate from research access by offering a different analysis environment. Clinical access would offer limited tools for data analysis to avoid abuse of privileges.

Data access review procedures

- Review time depends on the complexity of the request and needs for further clarification. The better prepared the instructions, data catalogue, service catalogue and application form, the more time can be saved as it will reduce feedback loops with users.
- It is necessary to establish clarity on the needs of the user with respect to the data, the processing environment and the analysis tools for drawing conclusions on the processing environment, which will influence choice of infrastructure, contractual arrangements and cost.
- The experienced reasons for delays in the review are largely:

- unclear / incomplete applications,
 - low frequency of DAC meetings,
 - low commitment of reviewers. The original data providers are often slow and also public authorities can take longer (e.g. DPAs and research ethics committees, that don't meet very often),
 - lack of funds, capacities and/or expertise of the review committees.
- Composition of the DAC:
- The tendency goes towards dedicated DACs rather than a review where the data were originally collected (e.g., hospitals, research institutes). Such "local" DACs suffer from lack of time, potential conflicts of interest and the quality of the feedback of the respective researcher / clinician.
 - The size of a dedicated DAC can be up to 20 people, and it may include patient and society representatives. Multi-disciplinary teams covering ethics, data protection, data science, IT security, genetics and relevant diseases should be considered, potentially some only in advisory and some in executive, i.e., decision making role. The inclusion of society and patient representatives may not be possible on a day-to-day working level but could be brought in in regular reviews of the work performed by the DAC.
 - Dedicated experts with sufficient capacity are needed for timely and high quality reviews.
- Further recommendations given by the group to improve quality and scalability of service for data access review by the 1+MG data infrastructure:
- High quality machine-actionable application form and good guidelines are essential to speed up the process. It must be clear to applicants what is requested; keep things / communication simple.
 - The need for direct interaction with the applicant must be foreseen despite a clear access request form and information materials. In particular to clarify technical questions, a discussion with the applicant may allow quicker clarification than back and forth written communication through the application form and response.
 - FAQs should be offered, well maintained and regularly updated.
 - Chatbots should be considered as a first line user interaction.
 - An internal quality assessment should be established to monitor user problems and act on them.

Data user and data use – Rejection of an access request

- Instead of stopping the clock when questions go back to applicants, the application could be rejected with an explanation of what was wrong / missing / unclear and invitation for reapplication. The reapplication should be easy for the user, i.e. the user must be able to reopen and adjust the previous application.
- This approach of rejection rather than joint exploration is not yet common but was seen as feasible in view of key performance indicators that have to be fulfilled. Nevertheless, it is going to be hard for the data access applicants at first, and good communication as well as a help desk to answer questions related to the rejection will still have to be planned for.
- Typical reasons (but not exhaustive) for rejections are
 - o An insufficient research plan that cannot justify the requested data (quality; quantity),
 - o missing, wrong or outdated ethics approvals,
 - o Unclear or unsuitable research question.

Data user and data use – Access fees

- There are no clear recommendations on financial models for data access provision.
- Scalability requires fees or other funding mechanisms for long-term sustainability. User related costs discussed by the experts were data access application handling costs, data preparation costs, data computing platform (SPE) related costs, technical support & help desk service for users. However, more data use cost will have to be considered such as accounting and user management based on federated identity and access management from 1+MG, archiving, administration etc.
- Potential risks of fees paid by requesters as identified in the discussions so far are
 - o Exclusion of certain groups of users (e.g. early stage researchers; financial divide across Europe where there are substantial differences in prices and salaries).
 - o Problems in obtaining funds if costs cannot be calculated in advance.
 - o Loss of trust from data subjects due to a perception that data are “sold”.

Further exploration of the advantages and disadvantages of user fees is needed.

- Administration cost for handling the fees should be taken into account and balanced against the gain from fees.

Data user and data use - Secure Processing Environment (SPE)

- Where SPEs are functional, they may even be an attractive solution for processing of user held data – it can be alternative to commercial cloud providers, where these do not offer the same level of data security and trust and can provide scalability of services and more expert advice on tools than often available at the user's host institute.
- However, SPEs can also be limiting where advanced processing is needed and/or the data are federated across different countries. Solutions must be found where the federation of the SPE as currently envisaged by the 1+MG Signatory Countries is not possible or to allow an advanced compute environment to be shared between different countries.
- The security provided by the SPE is key to build trust for data providers. Minimum requirements will have to be defined across 1+MG member countries.

Data user and data use – Misconduct by users

- Within SPEs, misconduct to breach privacy is much more difficult than when data are downloaded and the data infrastructure loses the physical control of the data processing. .
- Purpose limitation needs to be watched, both on the level of application (what qualifies for the actual categories of purposes) as well as within the system (e.g., through limiting tools to what is necessary for the approved use).
- Application of sanctions such as exclusion from ongoing use or future applications need to be foreseen, prepared and tested.

Data subjects rights

- **Most frequent question** is if any / which data are actually held by the data infrastructure. .
- Regular opt-outs are not to be expected. However, there may be waves of opt-outs due to external influence (e.g. public debate) for which the repository must be prepared.
- The impact of other data subjects' rights are likely negligible.

Retention time

- Data should not be deleted unnecessarily. Their usability for research or other secondary use purposes envisaged by the data infrastructure could be a criterion on which to build the retention time. The data retention time linked to usability is to be considered separate from

data retention for reproducibility of research purposes, which is relevant for establishing controls to ensure that data will not be kept longer than permitted.

- Criteria that have to be fulfilled for continued storage for secondary use should be SMART: specific, measurable, applicable to the respective data, relevant, and time-bound through periodically defined checks.

6. Discussion

We observe from the results of the two surveys that data governance for policy development is often modelled on considerations for research access, while data governance for quality management could be largely modelled on considerations for healthcare reuse. Arguments and examples given make us consider this approach, in particular including an ethics review for policy making purposes, for the 1+MG data infrastructure. The acceptability of a full review including ethics assessment has to be explored with the country representatives in the GDI Pillar I GOV working group. Such an approach may not be expected by the governmental representatives as ethics reviews for policy development is not practised in all countries. An example is the establishment of a health observatory in Luxembourg where the policy maker can pursue policies without a necessity to ask for ethics approval.²⁷ In these countries, it can happen that there is no competent ethics board that can give an ethics approval. On the other hand, there are countries that also do not foresee that researchers have to obtain an ethics approval for data research on the national level and the ethics committees therefore do not have a mandate to review such research either.²⁸ In consequence, the 1+MG data infrastructure may have to consider alternative procedures where a user cannot obtain an ethics review on the national level. However, the sensitivity of genomic data justifies the high ethical standards envisaged - where a harmonised data governance is the basis for the procedures, the highest standards should prevail.

Secondary use in the research context is fairly common, but at the same time, it is also the most complex and demanding with respect to procedures for data access review as well as for the infrastructure necessary. Special checks may have to be foreseen for the use of machine learning methods and artificial intelligence. Also other emerging methodologies will already require a flexible adjustment to needs. Research will always be at the forefront of these developments, which means that also 1+MG must be at the forefront of safeguards to protect the data. This applies also to the

²⁷ Law of March 2, 2021 establishing a National Health Observatory,
<http://legilux.public.lu/eli/etat/leg/loi/2021/03/02/a168/jo>

²⁸ See, e.g., Netherlands:
<https://english.ccmo.nl/investigators/legal-framework-for-medical-scientific-research/your-research-is-it-subject-to-the-wmo-or-not>

SPE, which must be able to provide for advanced computing while at the same time provide also sufficient guarantees for the privacy of the data in the system.

The experience of other data infrastructures teaches that a diligent design is needed if the later operations should be scalable. The clarity of the access request form and the quality of the information provided will be important for being able to streamline the application process. Also the supporting infrastructure is relevant for scalable procedures as it can reduce manual interaction. The consideration of a chat bot for user interaction is a good example for such support. The balancing of automated procedures and manual check-points will be an important element in the design.

Overall, the aim for best practice and to support data governance with IT infrastructure in a comprehensive way means that high investments will be needed, which could deter countries from a buy-in to the concept of an IT-supported data governance and access request administration. While scalability and quality should outweigh such concerns, it will still be a challenge to achieve best practice on a full scale.

Funding of investment and operations related costs remains an open issue with no clear solution. Challenges identified with respect to cost coverage mean that business models should weigh possibilities of different actors to contribute towards the investments and operational costs and benefits to be achieved. Highlighting the gains will be important.

The retention of data will be another subject that needs closer attention. Due to established customs of fixed time frames rather than criteria, the introduction of open ended retention where usability of data becomes a criterion will likely require alignment with the data protection authorities before such a scheme can be pursued. However, in terms of precedent - Austria has already established by law that data can keep data in principle indefinitely for future research use.²⁹ However, in case of 1+MG, we would rather establish criteria for a retention as required by Art. 13.2, 14.2 and 15.1.d GDPR, in line with Art. 5.2 GDPR on accountability. Apart from criteria related to the usability of data, also a balancing with the cost for storing will have to be considered.

The considerations on the 1+MG data governance are highly relevant for compatibility with the EHDS. The EHDS Regulation proposal in its form published on 3 May 2022 proposes a data access governance applicable to Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs). The current understanding is that 1+MG would qualify as an authorised participant under said Regulation acting independent of individual countries and their HDABs. While the EHDS Proposal explicitly mainly refers to technical compatibility requirements for authorised participants, the requirements for operating the cross-border infrastructure may include data governance related compatibility as well. From a

²⁹ Forschungsorganisationsgesetz §2d;

<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10009514>

logistics point of view, it is not yet clear to which extent an authorised participant can pursue its own data access governance. 1+MG should therefore at minimum cover the elements required by EHDS but we should strive to be able to keep up higher standards where applicable. Nevertheless it means that we are faced with a moving target that needs to be watched.

7. Conclusion

The experiences made by existing structures and data infrastructures that have already a mandate to decide on data access applications for secondary use provide valuable input into the considerations of the 1+MG data governance. Best practice or suggestions for changes to current practice should be taken into account. The option to support data governance with IT infrastructure tools is an attractive option for a scalable data infrastructure for secondary use.

Visions for an ideal implementation will have to be mapped against technical feasibility in exchange with Pillar II and the possibility to find acceptable financial models and the respective funding. Also legal and ethical aspects will still need to be further explored with relevant actors on the national and European level, such as data protection authorities. The surveys performed are important to inform the design of the 1+MG data governance but further explorations will be needed where the implementation is discussed in more detail and with additional stakeholders.

8. Next steps

The information on best practices and recommendations for data governance will be integrated into the proposed data governance that is under discussion in the GDI Pillar I GOV group.

The considerations for data governance as well as the discussion on user fees will provide input into the financial models in WP2. The updated data governance will be shared with Pillar II for consideration of the IT infrastructure enabling the data governance.

